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Good Governance Model for Poverty Alleviation Programmes in India

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Abstract :

The present study highlights that if there is Good Governance in the country it prevent 'unexpected surprised'. A well mechanized participation of good Governance in the poverty Alleviation Programmes can provide the country's sustainable growth, consistency of development, controlled and progress. The poverty alleviations programmes are classified into (i) self-employment programmes; (ii) wage employment programmes; (iii) food security programmes; (iv) Social security programme and (v) urban poverty alleviation programmes. The parameter used for evaluation included utilization of allocated funds, change in poverty level, employment generation and number or proportion of beneficiaries. The paper attempts to go beyond the economic benefit of the programmes and analyzes the social impact of these programmes on the communities where the poor, live and includes that too much of government involvement is actually an impediment. On the other hand, involvement of the community, especially the poor has led to better achievement of the goals of the programmes. Such endeavors not only reduced poverty but also empowered the poor to find their own solutions to their economic problems. There is a need for framing Good Governance in decentralization of the programmes by strengthening the Panchayat Raj institutions as poverty is not merely economic deprivation but also social marginalization that affects the poor most. If there is Good Governance model in the country it prevent 'unexpected surprised'. A well mechanized participation of good Governance model for the poverty Alleviation Programmes can provide the country's sustainable growth, consistency of development, controlled and progress. The parameter used for evaluation included utilization of authentic identification and model for eradicate and allocated funds, change in poverty level, reservation, employment generation and number or proportion of beneficiaries. The paper attempts to go beyond the economic benefit of the programmes and analyzes the social impact of these programmes on the communities where the poor, live and includes that too much of government involvement is actually an impediment.

Keywords: Introduction, Poverty alleviation programmes, Reservation system Framing of Good Governance for Poverty Eradication in India, Good Governance- Poverty Alleviation, Public Distribution System, Self employment, Social Marginalization, Social Security, Wage employment and Model of good Governance

1. Introduction

Since India became part of the global economy and undergoes economic reform in 1991, its economy is growing at a faster rate of nearly 10 per cent per annum. In the process, India has become the fourth largest economy in the world. In the last two decades, a significant proportion of the population across the country has reaped the benefits of this economic growth. They have become the part of global economy and market, citizens with all the comforts and luxury in life. Apart from this mass poverty is one of the Major Critical Problems confronting planners in India poverty can be defined as a social fact in which section of the society is unable to fulfill even its basic necessities of life.

The planning commission's new definition of poverty, based on the recommendations of the Suresh Tendulkar committee has now fixed a cut off of Rs.781 and Rs. 965 as the monthly per head expenditure in Rural and Urban areas respectively for a family to qualify as poor. But the World Bank has prescribed norms under which those living on less then \$ 1.25 a day (Rs. 56 a day or Rs. 1680 a Month) should be considered poor, that means India fulfill only half of this norms.

The traditional Method of defining poverty was based on how many calories people consumed. Going by the new definition, the planning commission has estimated the planning commission has estimated that nearly 37% of the country's people – 26 % of the urban population and 42% in the Rural areas - fall in to the Below poverty line (BPL) category.

However, the intention of this paper is not to join the debate on the level of poverty reduction in the country but to recognize the reduction of poverty in the country during the post- economic reforms era and to under take a good Governance for poverty alleviation programmes in this era of fast economic growth.

2. Poverty Estimation System in India

The data which released by planning commission in july 2013 is shows that the percentage of the population living below the poverty line in India decreased to 22% in 2011-12 from 37% in 2004-05. The Planning Commission conducted estimates levels of poverty in the country on the basis of surveys conducted by the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) of the Ministry of

Statistics and Programme accomplishment every five years. However, data from the 2009-10 survey has not been used in the official estimates of poverty as there was a rigorous drought in that year. The NSSO felt that this would introduce an abnormality in the results, and decided to repeat the survey in 2011-12.

Table 1, given below, shows national poverty levels for the last twenty years. According to these estimates, poverty declined at an average rate of 0.74 percentage points per year between 1993-94 and 2004-05, and at 2.18 percentage points per year between 2004-05 and 2011-12.¹

Year	Rural	Urban	Total
1993 – 94	50.1	31.8	45.3
2004 – 05	41.8	25.7	37.2
2009 – 10	33.8	20.9	29.8
2011 – 12	25.7	19.7	21.9

Table 1

Source: Press Note on Poverty Estimates, 2011 – 12, Planning Commission (2013), Government of India; Review of Expert Group to Review the Methodology for Estimation of Poverty (2009) Planning Commission, Government of India; PRS.

3. Study Methodology

Good Governance find in traces in every sectors of an economy and also in public governance which creates lots of problems for developing and poor country of the world, here we try to find out with the help of secondary published data with the help of giving transparency with new concept of model. Generally we find that the lack of good governance in public distribution system its cannot give birth to the fair and equal distribution in Government assistance to poor people which is the main provision of the failure of youjana and planning. Hence we should have to mould on some specific and authentic card numbers to identified the person to person . There is quite uncertainty of unexpected surprised in this world and every one need and wants transparency , authority and accountability in every fields. They re-grates for best utilization of public , private and corporate governance in his country and worldwide such for that there should be limitation to practice research and their implication to human being. There is every things in this universe which required to put an access of mankind and its utilization of resources , materials and also its causes and effects. In this Research paper we concluded with having conceptual aspects of social benefits and also for detection of disses . Last ally, here i have drawn a model to solved all the problems of this world to make free our world with vicious circle of poverty, corruption , terrorism ,murders, theft, blood group and its hr-factors to prevent healthy child birth and also, hermaphrodite, miscarriage and also more helpful to cure from root level of many hereditary dieses.

4. Poverty Alleviation Programmes

The programmes have been classified into self-employment programmes, wage employment programmes, food safety programme and social security programmes. The focus is on the central government schemes only. It is not possible to map the special programmes of all the States. It must be noted here that some of the progressive States have added additional components or given further subsidy to enhance the benefits of the central schemes. For example, in the highly subsidized public distribution system of Andhra Pradesh, the BPL Card holders were provided rice at Rs. 2 per kg. All the programmes here discussed in brief.

The eradication of poverty has been integral component of the strategy for economic development in India. Consistent with the objectives of successive plans in the realm of poverty alleviation, a number of general as well as specific programmes were implemented for improving the living conditions of the poor. However, in spite of these efforts, the problem of poverty continued to exist. The benefits did not percolate to lower levels because of adverse institutional framework. With the fifth Plan, poverty alleviation came to be accepted as one of the principal objectives of economic planning. strategy of direct assault on poverty through rural development and rural employment progrmmes was first adopted in the 1970s. The sixth plan sought to alleviate poverty through some specificS measures apart from relying on the overall higher rate growth of the economy. The integrated Rural Development Programme (IRD P) which was initially started in 1978-79 was not very effective as a poverty alleviation measures. It was restructured and renamed as Swarnajayanti Gram Swarozgar yojana (SGSY) in April 1999 and its allied programmes, viz TRYSEM, DWCRA, SITRA, GKY and MWS were merged with it. Jawahar Rozgar Yojana (JRY) was restructured and renamed as Jawahar Gram Samridhi Yojana (JGSY) in April 1999. The Employment Assurance Scheme (EAS) and Jawahar Gram Samridhi Yojana (JGSY) were merged into the Sampoorna Grameen Rozgar Yojana (SGRY) in September 2001. The Swarnajayanti shahari Rozgar Yojana (SJSRY) was lunched in December 1997. All the three Urban Poverty Alleviation Schemes, namely, urban basic services for the Poor (UBSP), Nehru Razgar Yojana (NRY) and Prime Minister's Integrated Urban Poverty Eradication Programme (PMI-UPEP) Were Merged with it.

The Annapurna Scheme was launched in April 2000. It aimed at providing food security to those senior citizens (65 year and above) who though eligible for the National old Age pension Scheme (NOAPS) remained uncovered under the Scheme. The Samagra Awaas Yojana, a Comprehensive Housing Scheme, was launched in April 1999. It ensured integrated provision of shelter, sanitation and drinking water. Elimination of poverty was one of the major objectives of the Eighth Plan. The schemes and

programmes aimed to provide food, health care, education; employment and shelter to the weaker sections were launched. The Ninth Plan relied essentially on the trickle down effects of economic growth for poverty alleviation.

The District Rural Industries Project (DRIP) was launched in October 1994 for providing employment opportunities for the rural poor by setting up rural industrial estates. For people below the poverty Line, Janashree Bima yojana, a group insurance scheme was launched in June 2000. Pradhan Mantri Gramodaya Yojana (PMGY) was introduced in 2000-01 to concentrate on villager level development. In November 2001, Swayamsidha Scheme was introduced for holistic women empowerment primarily on the self-help pattern. The government has set up Jai Prakash Rozgar Guarantee Yojana (JPRGY) in 2002-03 aimed at ensuring employment for people belonging to the most distressed districts of the country. NREGS (National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme) it is launched in the district during the year 2006, as per the National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (2005). The main objective of the programme is to provide 100 days of employment per each family in a financial year in rural areas it was renamed Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee scheme (MGNREGA) on 2nd October 2009. And For social security programmes are meant for those who are at the bottom of the BPL facing destitution and desertion. The central government has launched the National Social Assistance Programme or NSAP in August 1995. Under NSAP, there are three schemes. The first one is the National Old Ages Pension Scheme or NOAPS. A pension amount of Rs. 75 Per month is given to those who are the above the age of 65 years and are destitute without any regular source of income or support from any family member of relatives. Though it is a very useful scheme for the elderly destitute, the coverage of the programme was not satisfactory. In the year 1999-2000, 8.71 million eligible elderly were identified, but the scheme could reach out to only 5 million beneficiaries. It was found that the benefits really reached the poor and the leakage rate was to be found law.

5. Reservation System

The Present caste-based reservation system of Union Government Categorized as per Government of India reservation is on Percentage based as per Government of India

- Scheduled Castes (SC) 15%
- Scheduled Tribes (ST) 7.5%
- Other Backward Classes (OBC) 27%
- Total constitutional reservation percentage 49.5%

Mostly this is based on economic distribution system as using the words creamy layer Son(s)/daughter(s) of those who can earn 6 lakh (600,000) or more annually for three consecutive years are excluded from reservation. The creamy layer is only applicable in the case of Other Backward Castes and not applicable on other group like SC or ST. Though the efforts are also being made to do so. In some state the reservation within reservation has been made but creamy layer as such is applicable in OBCs only. But due to malpractices and corruption there is many more falsehood condition can be occurred and reliability of issuing or providing reservation is under suspense and which is creating lot of discrimination within them because we cannot able to decide who is really authorized for reservation ?

6. Framing of Good Governance for Poverty Eradication in India

While some of the poverty alleviation programme discussed above, may not be perform well in the terms of utilizing the allocated funds and increasing the income of the poor this programme have contributed to social arena of poverty. "Sirf Naam Badalne Se Tasvir Nahi Badalti" This is the ideal punch line for all the poverty programme which government of India was launched by the viewing above there should be required a good governance to stop unnecessary activities which constraint in the eradication of poverty programmes in India.

7. Good Governance

A good governance is about promoting fairness, transparency, accountability it is the system by which Government Policies, Programmes, Yojana & business corporation are directed and control.

The government of India required to follow good governance refers to exercise of political, economic, and administrative authority to manage the nation's affairs and the complex mechanism, process, relationship, and institution as well as leadership behavior through which citizens groups articulate their interests, exercise, their rights and obligations and mediate their differences. Governance is good when it is effective efficient and when the participations, interests, and livelihood of the governed are the prime motives of the leader's actions at every level of Society.

Good governance in not a matter of government only but a situation of multiple crisscrossing relationships in which different and various actors in the public and private sectors at national and international levels play various roles, some times mutually reinforcing and complimentary, sometimes conflicting, but always following the same principles and practices that are agreed as constituents of good governance.

Table 2: All the Institution which influenced for practicing Good Governance

In discussing issues of good governance and in designing and implementing the programme for strengthening good governance for poverty eradication, the government of India counts on the participations and contribution of all actors so that governance ceases to be an affair of only government.

An analysis of the out put of the consultations and discussion on good governance in the country shows that the situation of good governance may be this desegregated into:

- Good panchayat governance
- Good economy governance
- Good political governance
- Good managerial/administrative governance, and
- Good social or civic governance

Table 3: Good Governance for poverty reduction and socio political cultural livelihood

The social, political, economic and cultural livelihood of India is necessity by the interplay of these five levels of governance:

- Political governance is a combination of parliament of India, both government and private institutions systems, structures, processes, procedures, practices, relationships, and leadership behavior that empower the governed to influence the decisions and policies that concern them and to determine who governs them as well as through what ways.
- Economic governance is a combination of mixed economy and all the sectors which influence economy policies and its procedures, other institutions, systems, structures, processes, procedures, practices, relationships and leadership behavior that empower the governed to freely engage their initiatives and energies to undertake economic activity (production, distribution, and consumption) and expand their choices and enjoy better economic livelihood.
- Social or civil governance is a combination of both the public and private institutions, systems, structures, processes, procedures; practices, relationships, and leadership behavior that empower the governed to freely systematize themselves

and work to improve their livelihood and to challenge both public and private authorities take into account their problems. This is why the government of India it as crucial to promote the growth of a vibrant civil society in the country.

- Managerial/Administrative governance is a combination of all the institutions, systems, structures, processes, procedures, practices, relationships, and leadership activities that ensure effective, efficient economic and accountable planning, utilization, and control of resources for equitable and effective production and delivery of goods and services.
- Gram Panchayat governance is a combination of District level.(D.M.), Tahasil Level (Tahasildar/Law officer), Block Level (B.D.O./Gram vikash Adhikari) & village/Town Level (Gram Pradhan/Chairman) system structure, process, procedure, practices, relationship, and leadership behavior that make powerful the governed to influence the decisions and policies that concern them and to determine who governs them as well as through what ways.

A breakdown in any of the above components of the governance and livelihood balance will have a negative collision on the social, political, economic and cultural livelihood.

8. Esclation Good Governance for Poverty Reduction: Priority Thematic and Action Areas

In light of Indians vision of good governance, its poverty realities, achievements and challenges identified above, the following will be the priority areas where the Government with its partners in the private sector and civil society will concentrate action to strengthen good governance for poverty reduction in the coming years.

8.1. Past

Previous achievements: (Base for Building the Future)

- Constitutional amendment, modification and implications.
- Political reconstitution
- Peace and security
- Legislative authority & control
- Reconciliation, resettlement & re-integration
- Respect for Human rights
- Justice law & order
- Decentralization
- Constitution making process
- Electoral demoralization
- Empowering civil society
- Gender and women empowerment
- Managing the environment Combating HIV/AIDS
- Reforming the civil service
- Institutions for Transparency & accountability (Media, Office of the Auditor General)
- Institutions for economic management
- Foundations for HRD & Capacity building

8.2. Present

Current Challenges (Imperatives for Good Governance & Poverty Reduction)

- Completing the constitution making process
- Sustaining the democratization process
- Sustaining decentralization & people's empowerment
- Effective mechanisms of institutional coordination & harmony
- Strengthening Transparency and accountability
- Human resource development
- Reform, Professionalization & stabilization of civil service
- Sustaining the rule of & eliminating impunity
- Fostering national unity & reconciliation
- Respect & protection of human rights
- Sustaining peace & security
- Building Human capital
- Fighting HIV/AIDS & Malaria
- Providing Health for all
- Providing education for all
- Economic land use & natural resource management
- Promoting Gender equality & women empowerment
- Introducing ICT
- Promoting Civil society

- Strengthening private sector
- Strengthening the media
- Strengthening mechanisms for coordinated planning
- Strengthening Aid coordination

8.3. Future

Strategic Actions

- Make promulgate & implement the constitution
- Make elections a feature of Indians's politics
- Sustain decentralization
- Coordinate & harmonize government action
- Enforce transparency & accountability
- Develop the Human resource
- Professionalize & stabilize the Civil Service
- Enforce the rule of law & eliminate impunity
- Foster national unity & reconciliation
- Respect & protect human rights
- Sustain peace and security
- Build Human capital by: Mainstreaming the fight against HIV/AIDS
- Combating malaria
- Promote health for all
- Promote education for all
- Land use & environment and natural resource management
- Mainstream gender & empower women
- Strengthen ICT
- Promote & involve civil society
- Strengthen the media
- Develop private sector
- Strengthen national planning and financial management
- Strengthen coordination & management of aid

9. Applying Four Principles of Good Governance to Poverty Reduction

Having regard to international best practice, If India decided to apply four good governance principles to examining possible outcome indicators to be used to test the actual progress being made in the reduction of poverty. These are:

- Accountability- the obligation placed on government institutions and officials to give answers and explanations and to take responsibility for the impact of their actions on citizens- this provides the opportunity for citizens to have a voice and to participate in the affairs of Government;
- Transparency- this entails the free flow of low cost information that is understandable, reliable and timely;
- Participation- this refers to the opportunities available to citizens to participate in the affairs of government through mechanisms that give them a voice and influence in policy-making and program delivery;
- Predictability- refers to the rule of law and results primarily from laws and regulations and budgets that are clear, known in advance and uniformly and effectively enforced.

If these four principles are complied with, government is also likely to be efficient in the use of resources and also more effective in the sense of better achieving desired program outcomes. Thus, in applying these principles:

- Accountability, can be promoted through mechanisms for requiring that responses be made in respect of institutional conduct, and through appropriate incentives, good supervision, and high levels of citizen participation;
- Transparency, can be promoted by regular publication and dissemination of information, as well as through enhanced feedback loops among citizens, officials, and policy-makers;
- Participation, can be promoted through mechanisms that enable citizens to be more involved in the conduct of government, particularly through the implementation of appropriate decentralization policies; and
- Predictability, can be promoted through consistent application of rules and policies.

Applying these principles impinges very directly on the issue of what are the outcomes that are being achieved for the poor. They concern what is being achieved in empowerment of the poor in the sense of increasing their ability to contribute to government; to avail themselves of government services; to take advantage of economic and social opportunities that are available to them; and to do so in an environment in which their security is protected and their rights can be enforced.

10. Planning of Eradicating Poverty from India and the Poor Countries

- Identifies all the poor's and provide their children free and compulsory education up to some techniques degrees or knowledge to get job or develop entrepreneurial skill.
- Free Provide all the essentials of life i.e., food, cloths, shelter and medical remedies.

- Assist all the NGO's and other organization to identify poor's and provide data to government to take active role to make them aware of government plans and yojana.

10.1. Model of Good Governance

A Good Governance is necessary when ever some accountability of any form of Government can mandated in most transparent forms. But due to participation of Public Governance, Administration, State / provinces, management authority there found discrimination, corruption, poverty that were violated its all rules and regulation with mutual consideration which leads to happened unexpected surprise in any form of government and banks and some time it's bankrupted and closed for ever. There had been many reason of lock out. But the actual condition of growing at higher extent of discrimination, corruption, poverty and NPA is the most responsible of this prevalent. These types of destructive could not be managed and controlled by the management as well as central bank of any nation.

For controlling this type happening and bringing transparency it's required to have an authentic identification number to their people ,where its cover both demographic as well as biometric forms.:-

10.2. Demographic

- Name
- Father/husband name
- Mother name.
- Gender.....
- Date of birth.....
- Educational qualification.....
- (Its need to record all necessary of education)
- Income from ancestors.
- (Like land, building and capital etc.)
- Jobs.
- (It must be change when ever job changes by candidate and all
- Records should be mentioned by that institution)
- Banks account detailed.
- (All the bank details of holders must be interlinked and cover all the statement of His/her personal account, that is cash in banks / or loaning, share/bond /debenture etc.)

10.3. Biometrics

Eye iris + Finger prints + blood group + Rh factor
+ Photo of candidate.

Here biometrics is quite useful for the purpose of identifying the person and also it's quite helpful to solve the Health problem of people of the world and there is also solved the genetic diseases problems like impotent, hermaphrodite, miscarriage and also more helpful to cure from root level of many hereditary diseases.

In India there is Aadhaar card is working now days which is invented and explained by Professor. Nandan Nilekani but still it's not mandatory for their people and not so transparent to verify about their income/ job and ancestral property here I just try to explain in broader way for whole nation. Here it must be make compulsory to whole nation by providing unique identification number and that would be in algebraic form by using alphabetical letter of English. For example if it's going to made for Indian and state of Uttar Pradesh and in district Gorakhpur than its will be code like that:

For India use = I capital alphabetical letter

For Uttar Pradesh = UP and

For Gorakhpur = G

Now it will code as IUPG 01 , this number most go up to 10 Crores than after it should start with that way of form as (IUPG A01 And so, IUPG Z0100000000)

Its funding and responsibility will bear by World Bank and keep it confidential where it is necessity it can easily done and implemented through the help of all nation central bank and NGOs which can be brought this mission possible and eradicate all expected and unexpected surprise of banks and it's too easy to detect fraud and defaulters of loaning . Which not only save banks it's also protecting with corruption, poverty, unemployment etc. This can be easily make in process through government hospital as well as reputed Institution or village level official like Gram panchayat, block level etc.

It's also mandatory that there should be high level of software and confidential in protection that cannot be hacked and it can interlinked with every aspect of day today life. This not only reduces the burden of Government at also eradicate all the unexpected surprised. Now with this identification number we able to identify poor's and their condition to make policies and plans.

Than we can say that, "good governance model is about promoting fairness, transparency, accountability. It is the system by which government policies; programmes, yojana and Business Corporation, banking, and poverty, corruption reservation were directed and controlled."

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